

RELATIONSHIP OF PSORIASIS AND METABOLIC SYNDROME TO CHRONIC PERIODONTITIS- AN ORIGINAL STUDY

Authors :

1. Dr. Shilpa Shetty
Assistant Professor

Department of Periodontics
A.J Institute of Dental Sciences
Mangalore

2. Dr. Vinit B Patel
Associate professor

Department of public health dentistry
Faculty of dental science, DDU
Nadiad

3. Dr. Megha Vanasi
Assistant professor

Department of Periodontics
Faculty of dental science, DDU
Nadiad

4. Dr. Gayathri Murlidaran
Reader

Department of Periodontics
Mamata Dental College,
Khammam

Received: May 30, 2025

Accepted: July 01, 2025

Published: July 02, 2025

ABSTRACT

Background and objectives: The scientific literature linking periodontitis to metabolic syndrome has rapidly expanded. Psoriasis is a chronic inflammatory auto-immune disease. In recent years, strong evidence has been presented to support that psoriasis is associated with metabolic syndrome. The aim of this study was to assess the prevalence of periodontal disease in both psoriasis and metabolic syndrome patients compared to healthy subjects with chronic periodontitis. **Methodology:** In this case-control study, a total number of 80 subjects were selected from the Outpatient Department of A.J. Institute of Dental and Medical Sciences. Based on the clinical presentation and lab findings, the subjects were divided into four groups of 20 subjects each: Group 1: subjects with chronic periodontitis, Group 2: Patients with Psoriasis, Group 3: Patients with metabolic syndrome and Group 4: Patients with Psoriasis along with metabolic syndrome. The gingival and the periodontal status of all the teeth were assessed using the plaque index of Sillness and Loe, the gingival index of Loe and Sillness, probing depth (PD) and clinical attachment loss (CAL) by CPI index. Data obtained were statistically analyzed using ANOVA, Chi-square and Tukey's HSD tests. **Results:** The results of the study showed very high statistical significance for gingival and plaque index ($P < 0.001$); Group 1 showed higher mean values followed by Group 4, Group 3 and Group 2. The extent of periodontal disease as measured by probing pocket depth CPI (P Score) ($P < 0.001$) and loss of attachment ($P = 0.003$) was statistically significant. The percentage of sites with probing pocket depth (≥ 5 mm) was highest in

Group 1(100%) followed by Group 4 (80%) and Group 3(60%) and least in Group 2 (35%). Loss of attachment of > 3mm was highest in Group 1 (95%), Group 4 was (80%), Group 3 was (60%) and least in Group 2 (30%).

Interpretations and Conclusions: The data from this study shows that there is a higher prevalence of periodontal disease in patients with psoriasis and metabolic syndrome.

Keywords – Chronic Periodontitis, Psoriasis, metabolic syndrome.

INTRODUCTION:

Chronic periodontitis is defined as “an infectious disease resulting in inflammation within the supporting tissues of the teeth, progressive attachment loss, and bone loss.”¹ It has a multi factorial origin, and its course might be transient, undergoing cycles of exacerbations and spontaneous remissions.² Its activity is influenced by bacterial attack and host response. The host responds to the periodontal infections with an array of events involving both innate and adaptive immunity which target the destruction of alveolar bone and connective tissues.³

The Metabolic Syndrome is a constellation of interrelated risk factors of metabolic origin that appear to directly promote the development of atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease.⁴ Metabolic Syndrome is a combination of type 2 diabetes mellitus, hypertension, obesity and dyslipidaemia. There is a role for systemic inflammation, as a number of inflammatory markers are often increased in patients with MS (eg: C-reactive protein, interleukin IL-6 Or Tumour Necrosis Factor –alpha TNF- α).⁵

Generating an efficient and effective immune response involves large increase in cellular proliferation, biosynthetic and secretory activities, which require high energy consumption. Therefore, innate immune cells must be able to rapidly respond to the presence of pathogens shifting from a quiescent phenotype to a highly active site within hours of stimulation. For that purpose, cells must dramatically alter their metabolism to support their increased synthetic activities among which glucose is most essential. Hence, it can be hypothesized that periodontal inflammation is one of the sources of the low grade inflammation in patients with MS.⁶

Psoriasis is a chronic inflammatory autoimmune disease that affects about 3% of the population worldwide.^{7,8} Psoriasis can be associated with other diseases, which may have a major impact on the patients. The more common co-morbidities include psoriatic arthritis and anxiety/depression disorder.^{9,10,11} More recently, Psoriasis has been reported to be associated with metabolic disorders including obesity, dyslipidaemia and diabetes.^{12,13,14}

Both Psoriasis and periodontal diseases are characterized by an exaggerated response to the epithelial cell surface microbiota. The immune system further induces T cells to produce cytokines and these cytokines stimulate the proliferation of keratinocytes and production of antigenic adhesion molecules in dermal blood vessels. These adhesion molecules further stimulate T cells to produce cytokines, thus perpetuating the response.¹⁵ Hence, there might be a possible association in the pathogenesis of these two disease entities.

The aim of the present study is to investigate the prevalence of periodontal disease in both Psoriasis and MS patients compared to healthy controls.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

In this study, 80 participants, aged between 35- 64 years were examined from the outpatient Department Of Periodontics of A.J. Institute of Dental Sciences and outpatient Department Of Medicine and Dermatology of A.J. Institute of Medical Sciences. An informed consent was taken from all these subjects.

The inclusion criteria which were considered for the selection of subjects: included patients having Metabolic Syndrome, Patients having Psoriasis, Patients having Psoriasis along with metabolic syndrome and Subjects with more than three periodontal pockets with the probing depth of 5mm or more in each quadrant.

The patients who were excluded from the study are those who could not provide information or to co-operate with the dental examination, cannot accept periodontal treatment, have used the antibiotics for more than one week in the six months before the dental examination, patients diagnosed with cardiovascular, cerebrovascular or kidney disease or any known condition for which prophylactic antibiotic treatment before the dental examination is required, Smokers and individuals who consume alcohol and pregnant women or lactating women taking oral contraceptives.

According to the **International Diabetic Federation (IDF 2005) definition** for a person to be diagnosed with Metabolic Syndrome they must have:

Central obesity defined as waist circumference ≥ 90 cm for Asian men and ≥ 80 cm for women plus **any two** of the following four factors:

- **Elevated triglycerides** level ≥ 150 mg/dl or specific treatment for this lipid abnormality;
- **Reduced HDL cholesterol**: < 40 mg/dl in males and < 50 mg/dl in females or specific treatment for this lipid abnormality;
- **Elevated blood pressure (BP)**: systolic BP ≥ 130 mm Hg or diastolic BP ≥ 85 mm Hg or treatment or previously diagnosed hypertension; and
- **Elevated fasting plasma glucose (FPG)** ≥ 100 mg/dl or previously diagnosed type 2 diabetes.

These cut off values were used to diagnose a person with Metabolic Syndrome.

Body Mass Index and the waist circumference were calculated and fasting lipid profile and fasting plasma glucose levels were measured in all the 80 participants. Blood pressure levels were also monitored. Psoriasis was diagnosed based on clinical presentation which was carried out with the help of Department of Dermatology. Control group consisted of healthy subjects with chronic periodontitis .

Calculation of Body Mass Index:

Body weight in kilogram and height in meter were recorded and BMI was calculated for each individual using the formula:

$$\text{BMI} = \frac{\text{Body weight in kilograms}}{(\text{Height in meters})^2}$$

Blood sample collection

With the obtained blood fasting lipid profile (Total Cholesterol (TC), High Density Lipoprotein (HDL), Low Density Lipoprotein (LDL), very low density lipoprotein (VLDL)) and fasting blood glucose levels were obtained by enzymatic method.

Blood pressure:

Blood pressure was measured in all 80 participants using sphygmomanometer. Participants with systolic BP ≥ 130 mm Hg or diastolic BP ≥ 85 mm Hg or under treatment were considered hypertensive.

Periodontal Examination:

Periodontal status was assessed by using Modified Community Periodontal Index (m CPI), using a CPI probe (earlier called as CPITN (C) probe) .

All records were taken by single examiner. The highest CPI score found among all examined sites were concluded as CPI score for that individual. The gingival status of the individual was assessed by recording gingival index (**Loe and Silness, 1963**) and Plaque index (**Silness and Loe ,1964**).

Based on the medical examination and blood investigations, patients were divided into four groups of 20 subjects each.

Group 1	Healthy controls with chronic periodontitis
Group 2	Patients with Psoriasis
Group 3	Patients with metabolic syndrome
Group 4	Patients with Psoriasis along with metabolic syndrome

Statistical Analysis:

The obtained data was entered into Microsoft excel sheet. Means and standard deviations were used as descriptive statistics.

The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (15.0 J for Windows; SPSS Japan, Tokyo) was used for the statistical analyses. The results were tabulated in the form of tables. All the dental data were expressed on a patient basis. Data were presented as mean and standard deviation. Differences between means were proved for

significance using the one way ANOVA – test, chi- square test and multiple comparisons’ were done using Tukey’s HSD test.

The p-value of 0.05 or less was considered for statistical significance.

RESULTS:

BMI, waist circumference, fasting blood glucose level, fasting lipid profile and blood pressure were assessed in all the 80 subjects. The variations in gingival and periodontal status of all the four groups were determined.

Sex variation:

47 male and 33 female patients participated in the study. P value obtained was $P= 0.904$ and $X^2= 0.567$ showing that sex variation between the four groups was statistically insignificant (Table 1).

Plaque index:

ANOVA test was used to compare the plaque status between the 4 groups. The F value for the four groups was 23.05 and $P<0.001$ showing the plaque variation between four groups to be very highly significant (Table 2) (Graph I)

Tukey’s HSD test was used for multiple comparisons between the four groups.

- a) Plaque index compared between Group 1 and Group 2 showed $p<0.001$ which is very highly significant.
- b) Plaque index compared between Group 1 and Group 3 showed $p<0.001$ which is very highly significant.
- c) Plaque index compared between Group 1 and Group 4 showed $P=0.005$ which is highly significant.(Table 3)

Gingival index:

ANOVA test was used to compare the gingival status between the 4 groups. The F value for the four groups was 10.026 and $P <0.001$ showing the gingival status variation between four groups to be very highly significant. (Table 4) (Graph II)

Tukey’s HSD test was used for multiple comparisons between the four groups.

- a) Gingival index compared between Group 1 and Group 2 showed $P<0.001$ which is very highly significant.
- b) Plaque index compared between Group 1 and Group 3 showed $P<0.001$ which is very highly significant.
- c) Plaque index compared between Group 1 and Group 4 showed $P=0.013$ which is significant.(Table 3)

Correlation of modified community periodontal index in four groups

Chi-square test is used to find an association between CPI Index in the four groups.

Community periodontal index comprises of

1. CPI (G score)

The P value obtained was $P= 0.001$ and $X^2=41.616$ showing that CPI (G score) was statistically significant in the four groups, which indicated that both the test groups and control group had moderate to severe inflammation. (Table 5) (Graph III)

2. CPI (P score):

The P value obtained was $P< 0.001$ and $X^2=23.728$ showing that CPI (P score) was statistically significant in the four groups. (Table 6) (Graph IV).

3. Clinical attachment loss:

Clinical attachment loss in between the four groups was calculated using Chi square. The $X^2=24.856$ and $P=0.003$ which is statistically significant.(Table 7) (Graph V).

Since the CPI (G score) had $P < 0.001$, CPI (P score) had $P <0.001$, and clinical loss of attachment had $P = 0.003$, shows that overall community periodontal index was statistically significant.

Table 1 Sex variation

Sex		Groups				Total
		Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4	
Male	Count	11	13	12	11	47
	%	55.0%	65.0%	60.0%	55.0%	58.8%
Female	Count	9	7	8	9	33
	%	45.0%	35.0%	40.0%	45.0%	41.3%
Total	Count	20	20	20	20	80
	%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

$X^2 = .567$ $P = .904$ NS

Table 2

Plaque index

Group	N	Mean	Std.deviation
Group 1	20	2.900	.71818
Group 2	20	1.4500	.60481
Group 3	20	1.3000	.47016
Group 4	20	2.150	.87509

$F = 23.05$ $P < 0.001$ vhs

Graph I: Plaque index

Table 3

Multiple comparisons using Tukey's HSD test.

Dependent Variable	(I) group	(J) group	Mean Difference (I-J)	P
Gingival Index	Group 1	Group 2	.90000	<0.001 vhs
		Group 3	.75000	<0.001 vhs
		Group 4	.55000	0.013 sig
	Group 2	Group 3	-.15000	.829
		Group 4	-.35000	.201
	Group 3	Group 4	-.20000	.668
Plaque index	Group 1	Group 2	1.45000	<0.001 vhs
		Group 3	1.60000	<0.001 vhs
		Group 4	.75000	0.005 hs
	Group 2	Group 3	.15000	.899
		Group 4	-.70000	0.009 hs
	Group 3	Group 4	-.85000	<0.001 vhs

Table 4: Gingival index

Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Group 1	20	2.2500	.44426
Group 2	20	1.3500	.48936
Group 3	20	1.5000	.68825
Group 4	20	1.7000	.57124

F=10.026 P<0.001 vhs

Graph II: Gingival index

Table 5: Gingival bleeding score

Gingival bleeding score		Group				Total
		Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4	
.00	Count	0	8	12	4	24
	%	.0%	40.0%	60.0%	20.0%	30.0%
1.00	Count	20	12	8	16	56
	%	100.0%	60.0%	40.0%	80.0%	70.0%
Total Count		20	20	20	20	80
%		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

$X^2=41.616$ $P < 0.001$ sig

Graph III: Gingival Bleeding Score

Table 6 Pocket Score

Pocket score		Group				Total
		Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4	
.00	Count	0	13	8	4	25
	%	.0%	65.0%	40.0%	20.0%	31.3%
1.00	Count	13	6	7	8	34
	%	65.0%	30.0%	35.0%	40.0%	42.5%
2.00	Count	7	1	5	8	21
	%	35.0%	5.0%	25.0%	40.0%	26.3%
Total	Count	20	20	20	20	80
	%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

$X^2=23.728$ $P < 0.001$ vhs

Graph IV: Pocket score

Table 7: Loss of attachment

Loss of attachment		Groups				Total
		Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4	
.00	Count	1	14	8	4	27
	%	5.0%	70.0%	40.0%	20.0%	33.8%
1.00	Count	11	5	7	8	31
	%	55.0%	25.0%	35.0%	40.0%	38.8%
2.00	Count	6	1	4	4	15
	%	30.0%	5.0%	20.0%	20.0%	18.8%
3.00	Count	2	0	1	4	7
	%	10.0%	.0%	5.0%	20.0%	8.8%
Total	Count	20	20	20	20	80
	%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

$X^2=24.856$ P=.003sig

Graph V: Loss of Attachment

DISCUSSION:

In recent years, the potential of periodontal disease to cause disturbances in the systemic health has been discussed extensively. Periodontitis has been associated in previous literature with altered health conditions, (Kinane and Marshall 2001)¹⁶ such as diabetes, obesity and cardiovascular diseases. Recently, studies have suggested that periodontitis could also be associated with increased systemic inflammatory markers (Montebugnoli et al 2005)¹⁷, dyslipidaemia (Katz et al 2002)¹⁸, non fasting serum glucose alterations (Grossi and Genco 1998)¹⁹, endothelial dysfunction (Tonetti et al 2007)²⁰. These disturbances are a part of a specific metabolic state, “metabolic syndrome”²¹.

Psoriasis is a chronic inflammatory autoimmune disease affecting about 3% of the population worldwide. Psoriasis is characterized by epidermal hyperproliferation, abnormal keratinocyte differentiation; angiogenesis with blood vessel dilatation and excess Th-1 and Th-17 inflammation.²² The autoimmune type of inflammation of the skin has a strong genetic background, but is also influenced by environmental factors. Streptococcal infections may precipitate psoriasis.²³ Psoriasis is reported to be associated with cardiovascular disease, metabolic syndrome, rheumatoid arthritis, smoking, alcohol abuse, psychiatric disorders and stress.²⁴

Chronic destructive periodontal disease is a family of bacterial infections characterized by immunologically motivated destruction of periodontal supporting tissues.³ Both psoriasis and periodontal diseases are characterized by an exaggerated immune response to the microbiota residing on epithelial surfaces.¹⁵ Dendritic cells play an important role in driving an exaggerated immune response.^{25,26}

This case – control study investigated the prevalence of periodontal disease in both psoriasis and metabolic syndrome patients compared to healthy controls. A positive statistical association was found between periodontal disease, as measured by the probing depth and clinical attachment loss to metabolic syndrome.

Peng Li et al (2009)²⁷, did a case control study to assess the association of periodontitis with MS. Patients with MS had poor periodontal conditions and periodontal disease was associated with MS. The results of this study are similar to our study wherein the patients with MS had poor periodontal conditions.

Mitoshi et al (2009)²⁸, did a study on 1,070 Japanese people and examined the relationship between each component and the number of positive components of the MS. Periodontal status was assessed using CPI. The subjects with three components and those with four or five components had a significantly higher prevalence of a CPI code.

In this study, the gingival status of the individual was assessed using Gingival Index (Loe and Silness) and the Plaque Index (Silness and Loe). The gingival index which signifies the severity of gingival inflammation and the plaque index which signifies the oral hygiene status were statistically significant in the four groups ($P < 0.001$). Various mechanisms have been proposed to link gingival inflammation with metabolic abnormalities. Circulating concentrations of TNF- α or IL-6 are associated with BMI, but body fat distribution with particularly visceral adiposity more than total fat influence cytokine levels and hence there is endothelial activation. TNF- α induces production of IL-6 by adipose tissue and 30 % of total circulating IL-6 originates from adipose tissue.²⁹ Thus, the high level of gingival inflammation may be related to metabolic abnormalities of the inflammatory process.

Yousef Khader et al (2008)³⁰ conducted a study in 78 patients with MS and 78 patients without MS to estimate the prevalence of MS in northern Jordan. The oral hygiene status of six selected teeth and the periodontal status of all the teeth were assessed using the plaque index of Silness and Loe, the gingival index of Loe and Silness, probing depth and clinical attachment level. The probing depths of ≥ 3 mm and CAL ≥ 3 mm, were significantly greater among patients with MS compared to those without MS.

In the present study, patients with psoriasis exhibited periodontal destruction but the severity was less compared to MS patients. In patients with psoriasis along with MS, the severity of periodontal destruction was higher. Very few published studies have shown an association between psoriasis and chronic periodontitis. Both psoriasis and periodontitis share many common risk factors. Genetic and environmental factors are involved in the etiologies of these inflammatory diseases.^{31,32,33}

Ogorelkova et al³⁴ in their study stated that ‘an interesting hypothesis put forward was the idea that several diseases that are classified as distinct entities, such as psoriasis, periodontitis, and others, could all be included in a general category of inflammatory barrier disorders’. One mechanism for such a claim might be that the innate immune system is directing the subsequent adaptive immune responses (T and B cell responses), important in the pathogenesis of both psoriasis and periodontitis.^{35,36} Also, recent studies have demonstrated an up-regulation of Toll-like receptor (TLR)-2 in psoriatic skin,³⁷ and of periodontitis patients.³⁸ High expression of TLR will amplify the inflammatory reaction and sub-sequent T cell activation.

Additionally, periodontitis shares several important common pathways with psoriasis, including arachidonic acid, prostaglandin E₂ and leukotriene C₄, in its pathogenesis.³⁹ Also, vitamin D receptor (VDR) gene polymorphisms have been reported to be associated with psoriasis and periodontitis.^{40,41}

Hans Preus et al (2010)⁴² conducted a study on 155 psoriasis patients and 155 age and gender matched controls. Dental-bite wing X- rays were examined in both the groups. A significantly lower radiographic bone level and a significantly higher number of missing teeth were observed in the psoriasis compared to controls.

A case-control study conducted by Costa et al. (2021) was supposed to indicate the possible impact of periodontitis on the quality of life of patients with psoriasis. In fact, such individuals had a 1.4-times greater chance of periodontal disease, which was also shown in oral-health indexes such as the PCR, BOP, CAL, and PD. Those who suffered from psoriasis and periodontitis presented worse results of oral health in the quality-of-life parameter. Additionally, there was a significant association between periodontitis and the psoriasis severity and quality of life related to oral health.⁴³ Sarac et al.(2017)⁴⁴ evaluated the role of periodontitis and determined whether it might affect psoriasis. The study showed a relation between the conditions of these two diseases. It was noted that the community periodontal index of treatment needs was significantly higher for the patients as opposed to the control representatives, implying the worse condition of the former.

A case-control study conducted by Costa et al.⁴⁵ was supposed to indicate the possible impact of periodontitis on the quality of life of patients with psoriasis. In fact, such individuals had a 1.4-times greater chance of periodontal disease, which was also shown in oral-health indexes such as the PCR, BOP, CAL, and PD. Those who suffered from psoriasis and periodontitis presented worse results of oral health in the quality-of-life parameter. Additionally, there was a significant association between periodontitis and the psoriasis severity and quality of life related to oral health.

Limitations of the study:

A number of limitations must be considered in the present study:

1. The design of this study does not allow interpretation of a temporal relationship between the exposure and the outcome.
2. The recruitment of subjects from a single site may affect the outcome of our findings.
3. Other confounding variables such as diet, exercise, stress history etc were not considered for the study because these factors might be responsible for some of the putative associations like socio economic status, lifestyle characteristics etc.

CONCLUSION:

Periodontists must be aware of the increasing numbers of persons with metabolic disorders and of the significance of MS and Psoriasis as a multiple-risk factor syndrome for overall general and oral health. Recent cross-sectional and prospective studies have indicated a close correlation of MS with periodontal disease and with other chronic inflammatory diseases, including type 2 diabetes and cardiovascular diseases. Whether the relationship between MS and periodontitis is causal, needs to be assessed in future studies. Pro-inflammatory cytokines may be a multidirectional link among periodontitis, MS, psoriasis, and other chronic diseases. The pro- atherogenic changes in plasma lipids and blood glucose that were observed in periodontitis patients may provide further evidence for the close association between periodontitis and cardiovascular diseases.

In our clinical study, patients with MS showed greater prevalence of periodontal disease. Therefore, in-depth knowledge regarding the possible source of increased inflammatory burden in patients with MS and psoriasis is necessary in order to provide efficient general and oral health care.

Further research is required to determine whether causal relationship exists between MS and periodontal disease and if so to investigate the impact of therapeutic actions taken to reduce the effect of insulin resistance on periodontal disease. The magnitude of periodontal destruction in psoriasis patients was inconclusive. However, both psoriasis and periodontitis share many common risk factors.

REFERENCES:

1. M. John Novak and Karen F . Novak. Chronic Periodontitis. Carraza's Clinical Periodontology 11th ed.
2. Cripps. Periodontal disease. Recognition, Inception and Prevention. 4th ed St Loius Mosby.1984
3. Giannobile W V. Host response therapeutics for periodontal diseases. J Periodontol 2008;79:1592-1600.
4. National Cholesterol Education Program (NCEP) Expert Panel on Detection, Evaluation and Treatment of High Blood Cholesterol in (Adults Treatment Panel III). Third Report of the National Cholesterol Education Program (NCEP), Expert Panel on Detection, Evaluation and Treatment of High Blood Cholesterol in Adults(ATP III), final report, Circulation 2002;106:3143-3421.

5. Arnon D Cohen, Harel Gilutz, Yaakov Henkin, Doron Zahger, Jonathan Shapiro, Dan Y. Bonne and Daniel A. Vardy. Psoriasis and the Metabolic Syndrome. *Acta Derm Venerol* 2007; 87:506-509.
6. Wolowczuk I, Verwaerde C, Viltart O, et al. Feeding our immune system: Impact on metabolism. *Clin Dev Immunol* 2008;639803.
7. Schon M P, Boenhckl WH. Psoriasis N.Eng J.Med 2005;352:1899-912.
8. Krueger G, Ellis CN, Psoriasis. Recent advances in understanding its pathogenesis and treatment. *J Am Acad Dermatol* 2005;53:S 94-100.
9. Gisondi P, Girolomoni G, Sampogna F et al. Prevalence Of Psoriatic Arthritis And Joint Complaints In A Large Population Of Italian Patients Hospitalised For Psoriasis. *Eur J Dermatol* 2005;15:279-283.
10. Gelfande JM, Gladman DD, Mease PJ et al. Epidemiology Of Psoriatic Arthritis In The Population Of The United States. *J Am Acad Dermatol* 2005;53:573.
11. Kimball AB, Jacobson C, Weiss S et al. The Psychosocial Burden Of Psoriasis. *Am J Clin Dermatol* 2005;6:383-392.
12. Henseler T, Christophers E. Disease Concomitans In Psoriasis. *J Am Acad Dermatol* 1995;32:982-6.
13. Neimann A L ,Shin D B ,Wang x et al. Prevalence of cardiovascular risk factors in patients with psoriasis. *J Am Acad Dermatol* 2006;55:829-835.
14. Mallbris L, Ritchlin C J, Stahle M . Metabolic disorders in patients with psoriasis and psoriatic arthritis. *Curr rheumatol Rep* 2006;8:355-363.
15. Asadullah K, Vock H D , Sterry W. Novel immunotherapies for psoriasis. *Trends Immunol* 2002;23:47-53.
16. Kinane DF and Marshall G J. Periodontal manifestations of systemic disease. *Australian Dental Journal* (2001);46:2-12.
17. Montebugnoli L, Servidio D, Miaton R.A, Prati C, Tricoci P, Melloni C, and Melandri G.Periodontal health improves systemic inflammatory and haemostatic status in subjects with coronary heart disease. *J Clin Periodontol* 2005;32:188-192.
18. Katz J, Flugelman M .Y, Goldberg A and Heft M .Association between periodontal pockets and elevated cholesterol and low density lipoprotein cholesterol levels. *J Periodontol* 2002;73:494-500.
19. Grossi.S and Genco R.J.Periodontal disease and diabetes mellitus:a – two way relationship. *Ann Periodontol* 1998:51-61.
20. Tonetti, M. S., D’Aiuto, Nibali, L., Donald. A., Storry. C. Parkar, M. et al. Treatment of periodontitis and endothelial function. *New England Journal of Medicine* 2007;356:911-920.
21. Catherine Benguigui, Vanina Bongard, Jean-Bernard Ruidavets, Bernard Chamontin, Michel Sixou, Jean Ferrieres And Jacques Amar. Metabolic syndrome, insulin resistance and periodontitis: a cross sectional study in a middle French population. *J Clin Periodontal* 2010;37:601-608.
22. Rahat S. Azfar and Joel M. Gelfand. Psoriasis and metabolic disease: Epidemiology and Pathophysiology. *Current Opinion in Rheumatology* 2008;20: 416-422.
23. Telfer NR, Chalmers RJ, Whale K, Colman G. The Role Of Streptococcal Infection In The Initiation Of Guttate Psoriasis. *Arch Dermatol* 1992;128:39-42.
24. Gottlieb AB, Shao C, Dann F,. Psoriasis Comorbidities. *J Dermatol Treat* 2008;19:5-21.
25. Cutler CW, Jotwani R. Dendritic Cells At The Oral Mucosal Interface. *J Dent Res* 2006;85:678-89.
26. Sabat R, Philipp S, Hoflich C, Kreuezer S, Wallace E, Asadullah K, et al. Immunopathogenesis Of Psoriasis. *Exp Dermatol* 2007;16:779-98.
27. Peng Li, Lu He, Yue-qin Sha, and Qing-xian Luan ; Relationship of Metabolic Syndrome to Chronic Periodontitis. *J Periodontol* 2009;80:541-549.
28. Mitoshi Kushiya, Yoshihiro Shimazaki ,and Yoshihisa Yamashita ;Relationship Between Metabolic Syndrome and Periodontal Disease in Japanese Adults. *J Periodontol* 2009;80:1610-1615.
29. Ziccardi P, Nappo F, Esposito K, Cioffi M, Molinari AM. Reduction of inflammatory cytokine concentrations and improvement of endothelial functions in obese women after weight loss over one year. *Circulation* 2002;105:804.
30. Yousef Khader, Basheer Khassawneh, Basel Obeidat, Mohammad Hammad, Khalid El-Salem, Hiba Bawadi, and Nemeh Al-akour ; Periodontal Status of Patients with Metabolic Syndrome Compared to Those Without Metabolic Syndrome. *J Periodontol* 2008;79:2048-2053.
31. Gudjonsson JE, Elder JT. Psoriasis: Epidemiology. *Clin Dermatol* 2007;25:535-546.
32. Giardina E, Sinibaldi C, Novellig. The Psoriasis Genetics as A Model Of Complex Disease. *Curr Drug Targets Inflamm Allergy* 2004;3:129-36.
33. Offenbacher S. Periodontal Diseases:Pathogenesis. *Ann Periodontal* 1996;1:821-878.

34. Ogorelkova M and Estivill X. Human genetics moves from clinic to bench - and back. *Genome Biology* 2005; 6:343.
35. Candia L, Marquez J, Hernandez C, Zea AH, Espinoza LR. Toll like receptor-2 expression is upregulated in antigen presenting cells from patients with psoriatic arthritis; a pathogenic for innate immunity. *J Rheumatol* 2007;34:374-379.
36. Mahanonda R, Pichyangkul S. Toll like receptors and their role in periodontal health and disease. *Periodontol* 2000; 2007;43:41-55.
37. Hurst J, von Landenberg P. Toll-like receptors and autoimmunity. *Autoimmune Rev* 2008;7:204–8.
38. Burns E, Bachrach G, Shapira L, Nussbaum G. Cutting edge:TLR2 is required for the response to porphyromonas gingivalis:activation leads to bacterial persistence and TLR2 deficiency attenuates induced alveolar bone resorption. *J Immunol* 2006;177:8296-300.
39. Alam SQ, Bergens BM, Alam BS. Arachidonic acid, Prostaglandin E2 and Leucotriene C4 levels in gingiva and sub-mandibular salivary gland of rats fed diet containing n-3 fatty acids. *Lipids* 1999; 26:895-900.
40. Kaya TI, Erdal ME, Tursen U, Camdeviren H, Gunduz O, Soyleniz F, et al. Association between vitamin D receptor gene polymorphism and psoriasis among the Turkish population.
41. Inagaki K, Krall EA, Fleet JC and Garcia RI. Vitamin D receptor alleles, periodontal disease progression, and tooth loss in the VA dental longitudinal study. *J Periodontol* 2003;74:161-7.
42. Hans R. Preus, Pejman Khanifam, Kristin Kolltveit, Cato Mørk and Per Gjermo. Periodontitis in psoriasis patients. A blinded, case-controlled study. *Acta Odontologica Scandinavica*, 2010;68:165–170.
43. Costa A.A., Cota L.O.M., Mendes V.S., Oliveira A.M.S.D., Cyrino R.M., Costa F.O. Periodontitis and the Impact of Oral Health on the Quality of Life of Psoriatic Individuals: A Case-Control Study. *Clin. ORAL Investig.* 2021;25:2827–2836. doi: 10.1007/s00784-020-03600-1.
44. Sarac G., Kapicioglu Y., Cayli S., Altas A., Yologlu S. Is the Periodontal Status a Risk Factor for the Development of Psoriasis? *Niger. J. Clin. Pract.* 2017;20:474–478. doi: 10.4103/1119-3077.204371.
45. Costa A.A., Cota L.O.M., Mendes V.S., Oliveira A.M.S.D., Cyrino R.M., Costa F.O. Periodontitis and the Impact of Oral Health on the Quality of Life of Psoriatic Individuals: A Case-Control Study. *Clin. ORAL Investig.* 2021;25:2827–2836. doi: 10.1007/s00784-020-03600-1.